

Accelerating Kantowski-Sachs Universe in $f(Q, T)$ Gravity

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Abstract

The present investigation deals with the $f(Q, T)$ gravity, which was recently attracted attention of many cosmologists. In this theory, the gravitational action is formulated using an arbitrary function $f(Q, T)$ where Q represents the non-metricity scalar and T denotes the trace of the energy-momentum tensor. In this paper, we have investigated Kantowski-Sachs cosmological models in the context of $f(Q, T)$ gravity under the influence of wet dark fluid. A functional form $f(Q, T) = \alpha Q + \beta T$, where α and β are constants, is chosen for derivation. We analyze three different models and obtained the exact solution of the field equations by considering i) special form of deceleration parameter $q = -1 + \frac{\gamma}{1+a^\gamma}$ ii) hyperbolic scale factor $a(t) = \sinh(\eta t)$ iii) the scale factor $a(t) = te^t$ which generates a time-dependent deceleration parameter. We also studied some physical and kinematical parameters of the investigated models and discussed their behavior graphically.

Keywords: Kantowski-Sachs spacetime; $f(Q, T)$ gravity; Wet dark fluid; Deceleration parameter.

I. INTRODUCTION

The behavior of large-scale objects like galaxies, galaxy clusters, stars and planets are explained by gravity. The concept of gravity in curvature has reshaped our understanding of the universe, which consists of two essential components: dark energy and dark matter [1-3]. These components play a main role in expanding universe. The swift expansion of the universe is believed to result from a mysterious force with negative pressure named dark energy (DE). Analytical studies seek to find whether DE is the sole cause for the universe's acceleration or other factors are involved. Such ambiguities have sparked a search for a new approach on general relativity [4-6]. To accommodate new findings, there are mainly two approaches: one is to propose alternative theories of gravity and the other is to modify Einstein's general relativity. Different modified theories of gravity such as $f(G)$ gravity [7], $f(R)$ gravity [8], $f(R, T)$ gravity [9], $f(T)$ gravity [10], $f(Q)$ gravity [11] and the recently proposed $f(Q, T)$ gravity [12] has been developed to investigate the properties of dark energy and the accelerated expansion of the universe.

In recent years, modified gravity theories have garnered considerable interest as potential solutions to problems in cosmology such as the nature of dark energy, dark matter and the universe's late-time accelerated expansion. Among these modified theories, $f(Q, T)$ gravity which is proposed by Yixin Xu et al. [12], gives a novel approach by incorporating both the non-metricity scalar Q and the trace of the energy-momentum tensor T . This framework broadens the scope of modified gravity theories by introducing a novel interaction between matter and geometry. $f(Q, T)$ gravity alters the geometric structure of spacetime by taking a function f of the non-metricity of spacetime Q and T , representing the matter content. This theory stands out as it generalizes metric theories, providing a rich structure that can encapsulate various gravitational phenomena within a single framework. $f(Q, T)$ gravity can feasibly yield insights into how matter influences spacetime geometry in ways not accounted for in General relativity. Yixin et al. [12] investigated the $f(Q, T)$ gravity in three specific models. The solutions obtained capture both accelerating and decelerating phases of cosmic evolution, implying that $f(Q, T)$ gravity provides significant insights into the early and late stages of cosmological evolution. Despite being relatively new, the theory has found applications in the literature. Arora et al. [13-14] have studied the viability of the $f(Q, T)$ gravity, as an approach to explain cosmic acceleration and provide a plausible solution to the dark energy problem. They also examined the energy conditions in $f(Q, T)$ gravity [15-16]. The cosmological perturbation theory in the context of $f(Q, T)$ gravity has been discussed in [17]. Gadbail et al. [18] have reconstructed the $f(Q, T)$ models for diverse cosmological scenarios and demonstrated the model's validity. In [19], the authors develop a completely covariant formulation of the $f(Q, T)$ theory. By applying this formulation, they derive the correct energy balance equation and conduct a dynamical system analysis in FLRW spacetime. Recently Mete et al. [20] have studied Bianchi type-V cosmological model in $f(Q, T)$ gravity.

One of the most drastic challenges in cosmology is clarifying the mystery of dark energy. Recent observations indicate that the universe is currently expanding. In this regard, we are inclined to utilize the wet dark fluid as a framework to represent dark energy. This selection is influenced by the equation of state suggested by Tait [21] and Hayward [22], typically used to characterize the attributes of water and aqueous solutions. The wet dark fluid's equation of state is given as

$$p_{WDF} = \omega(\rho_{WDF} - \rho^*) \quad (1)$$

where p_{WDF} , ρ_{WDF} represents pressure and energy density of wet dark fluid respectively. The parameters ω and ρ^* are taken to be positive with ω restricted to the range $0 \leq \omega \leq 1$. To find the energy density, we use the energy conservation equation

$$\dot{\rho}_{WDF} + 3H(p_{WDF} + \rho_{WDF}) = 0 \quad (2)$$

Using equation (1) and substituting $3H = \frac{\dot{V}}{V}$, we get

$$\rho_{WDF} = \frac{\omega}{1+\omega} \rho^* + \frac{c}{V^{(1+\omega)}} \quad (3)$$

where V is the volume expansion and c is an integration constant.

It's noteworthy that wet dark fluid consists of two components: one part behaving as a cosmological constant and another part acting as a conventional fluid with the equation of state $p = \omega\rho$.

If $c > 0$, then this fluid will satisfy strong energy condition, $p + \rho \geq 0$.

Thus, we get

$$p_{WDF} + \rho_{WDF} = (1 + \omega)\rho_{WDF} - \omega\rho^* = (1 + \omega) \left(\frac{c}{V^{(1+\omega)}} \right) \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

Kaluza-Klein universe by considering a wet dark fluid as the matter content in $f(R, T)$ theory of gravity is investigated by Munde [23] recently. Dhote and Deo [24] examined five-dimensional plane symmetric model having wet dark fluid in $f(R)$ theory. Agrawal and Nile [25] studied Bianchi type-III metric incorporating a wet dark fluid in the framework of $f(R)$ theory of gravity. Wankhade et al. [26] examined the impact of wet dark fluid on Bianchi type VIII model in Barber self-creation theory. Singh et al. [27] studied the essence of $f(R, T)$ theory in five-dimensional Kaluza-Klein with wet dark fluid.

In addition to Bianchi-type metrics, the Kantowski-Sachs [28] models also describe spatially homogeneous universe. These metrics depict homogeneous but anisotropically expanding (or contracting) cosmologies and offer models in which the effects of anisotropy can be evaluated and compared with the familiar FRW class of cosmologies. Some notable researchers who have explored such models are [29-30]. Wath and Nimkar [31] investigated Kantowski-Sachs models in presence of Saez-Ballester scalar tensor theory of gravitation. Landry [32] examined spherically symmetric solutions of Kantowski-Sachs models in Teleparallel gravity. Vinutha et al. [33] have worked on Kantowski-Sachs cosmological model in $f(R, T)$ gravity. Bhojar et al. [34] discussed Kantowski-Sachs space-time with perfect fluid quadratic equation of state in $f(T)$ gravity. Khade et al. [35] have explored the role of variable deceleration parameter in Kantowski-Sachs space time with bulk viscous string in $f(R, T)$ gravity.

Motivated by the above discussion, in this paper we investigate Kantowski-Sachs space-time with wet dark fluid in the context of $f(Q, T)$ gravity. The paper is organized as follows: section II focuses on formalism of $f(Q, T)$ gravity. The metric and field equations are discussed in section III. Section IV deals with solution of the field equations in three models. Section V is concerned with discussion about graphical representation of physical parameters of obtained models. The last section contains a conclusion.

II. FORMALISM OF $f(Q, T)$ GRAVITY

The action principle of $f(Q, T)$ gravity which is a function of matter Lagrangian L_m is read as,

$$S = \int \left(\frac{1}{16\pi} f(Q, T) + L_m \right) \sqrt{-g} d^4x \quad (5)$$

where g is the metric determinant of the fundamental tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$, $f(Q, T)$ is an arbitrary function of the non-metricity Q and the trace of the matter-energy-momentum tensor T , L_m is the usual matter Lagrangian. The non-metricity Q is given by,

$$Q = -g^{\mu\nu}(L^\alpha_{\beta\mu}L^\beta_{\nu\alpha} - L^\alpha_{\beta\alpha}L^\beta_{\mu\nu}) \quad (6)$$

where $L^\alpha_{\beta\gamma}$ denotes the deformation tensor which is given by,

$$L^\alpha_{\beta\gamma} = -\frac{1}{2}g^{\alpha\delta}(\nabla_\gamma g_{\beta\delta} + \nabla_\beta g_{\delta\gamma} - \nabla_\delta g_{\beta\gamma}) \quad (7)$$

The trace of matter-energy-momentum tensor T and non-metricity Q are defined respectively as

$$T_{\mu\nu} = -\frac{2}{\sqrt{-g}} \frac{\delta(\sqrt{-g}L_m)}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}}, \quad Q_\alpha \equiv Q^\mu_{\alpha\mu} \quad (8)$$

The field equation of $f(Q, T)$ gravity is obtained by varying the gravitational action (5) with respect to metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ as

$$-\frac{2}{\sqrt{-g}}\nabla_\alpha(f_Q\sqrt{-g}P^\alpha_{\mu\nu}) - \frac{1}{2}f g_{\mu\nu} + f_T(T_{\mu\nu} + \Theta_{\mu\nu}) - f_Q(P_{\mu\alpha\beta}Q^\alpha_{\nu\beta} - 2Q^\alpha_{\mu\beta}P_{\alpha\beta\nu}) = 8\pi T_{\mu\nu} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\Theta_{\mu\nu} = g^{\alpha\beta} \frac{\delta T_{\alpha\beta}}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} \quad (10)$$

and $f_Q = \frac{\partial f(Q,T)}{\partial Q}$, $f_T = \frac{\partial f(Q,T)}{\partial T}$ and $P^\alpha_{\mu\nu}$ is the superpotential of the model which is defined as

$$P^\alpha_{\mu\nu} = -\frac{1}{2}L^\alpha_{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{4}(Q^\alpha - \tilde{Q}^\alpha)g_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{4}\delta^\alpha_{(\mu}Q_{\nu)} \quad (11)$$

III. METRIC AND FIELD EQUATIONS

The spatially homogeneous and anisotropic Kantowski-Sachs space time is given by

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - A^2 dr^2 - B^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2) \quad (12)$$

where the scale factors A, B are functions of cosmic time t only.

The cosmological models of Kantowski-Sachs metric exhibit two symmetry properties, namely spherical symmetry and spatial translational invariance. It describes a spatially homogeneous, anisotropic universe and the interior of black holes, which doesn't allow a straightforward transitive motion group. It is also used to examine the behavior of added degrees of freedom in quantum cosmological models. This metric represents three distinct anisotropic 3+1 dimensional spacetimes with positive curvature [33]. Research on anisotropic models has been nourished by CMB observations and theoretical studies, extending to modified gravity theories.

Here we have taken an effort to construct a cosmological model in this space-time with wet dark fluid (WDF). The energy momentum tensor for wet dark fluid is given by

$$T_{ij} = (p_{WDF} + \rho_{WDF})u_i u_j - p_{WDF}g_{ij} \quad (13)$$

where ρ_{WDF} and p_{WDF} are energy density & pressure of the wet dark fluid. $u^i = (1, 0, 0, 0)$ is the four-velocity vector of the fluid satisfying the relation $u_i u^i = 1$ & $u^i \nabla_j u_i = 0$.

In comoving coordinate system, we have

$$T^1_1 = T^2_2 = T^3_3 = -p_{WDF}, \quad T^0_0 = \rho_{WDF}, \quad T = -3p_{WDF} + \rho_{WDF} \quad (14)$$

θ_j^i is derived as

$$\theta_j^i = \delta_j^i p_{WDF} - 2T_j^i = \text{diag} (p_{WDF} - 2\rho_{WDF}, 3p_{WDF}, 3p_{WDF}, 3p_{WDF}) \quad (15)$$

The non-metricity tensor Q for given cosmological model is found to be

$$Q = -2 \left(\frac{\dot{B}^2}{B^2} + 2 \frac{A\dot{B}}{AB} \right) \quad (16)$$

The field Eq. (9) with the help of components of energy momentum tensor provided in Eq.(14),also using Eqs. (15) and (16) for the metric(12) are obtained as,

$$\frac{1}{2}f + 2F \left(\frac{\dot{B}^2}{B^2} + 2 \frac{A\dot{B}}{AB} \right) = -8\pi(1 + \tilde{G})\rho_{WDF} + 8\pi\tilde{G}p_{WDF} \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}f + 2F \left(\frac{\dot{B}}{B} + \frac{\dot{B}^2}{B^2} + \frac{A\dot{B}}{AB} \right) = 8\pi(1 + 2\tilde{G}) p_{WDF} \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}f + F \left(\frac{\dot{A}}{A} + \frac{\dot{B}}{B} + \frac{\dot{B}^2}{B^2} + 3 \frac{A\dot{B}}{AB} \right) = 8\pi(1 + 2\tilde{G}) p_{WDF} \quad (19)$$

where $F = f_Q$, $f_T = 8\pi\tilde{G}$ and an overhead dot represents ordinary differentiation with respect to time. The average scale factor a and the spatial volume V are defined as

$$a = (AB^2)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (20)$$

$$V = a^3 = AB^2 \quad (21)$$

The mean Hubble parameter H is given by

$$H = \frac{1}{3}(H_1 + H_2 + H_3) \quad (22)$$

where $H_1 = \frac{\dot{A}}{A}$, $H_2 = H_3 = \frac{\dot{B}}{B}$ are the directional Hubble parameters for the coordinates r, θ, φ respectively. The expansion scalar θ and the shear scalar σ^2 are given by

$$\theta = u^\alpha{}_{;\alpha} = \frac{\dot{A}}{A} + 2 \frac{\dot{B}}{B} \quad (23)$$

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{i=1}^3 H_i^2 - \frac{\theta^2}{3} \right] = \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{\dot{A}}{A} - \frac{\dot{B}}{B} \right)^2 \quad (24)$$

The anisotropy parameter of the expansion Δ is defined as

$$\Delta = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=1}^3 \left(\frac{H_i - H}{H} \right)^2 \quad (25)$$

The deceleration parameter q is defined as

$$q = -\frac{a\ddot{a}}{\dot{a}^2} \quad (26)$$

IV. SOLUTIONS OF THE FIELD EQUATIONS

There are different functional forms of $f(Q, T)$ gravity [12]. In the present study, we take the linear form $f(Q, T) = \alpha Q + \beta T$ where α and β are constants.

Here $F = f_Q = \alpha$, $f_T = \beta = 8\pi\tilde{G}$, $\tilde{G} = \frac{\beta}{8\pi}$.

The fields equations (17)-(19) are system of three independent equations in four unknowns. $A, B, p_{WDF}, \rho_{WDF}$. Hence to obtain determinate solution of the system, we require some extra conditions. Firstly, we assume that the expansion scalar θ is proportional to shear scalar σ which is used by Collins et al. [36], which results into linear relationship between two metric coefficients in terms of A and B as

$$A = B^n \quad (27)$$

where n is an arbitrary constant such that for $n \neq 1$, the space time is anisotropic nature. The physical justification for assuming this condition is that Hubble expansion of the universe can achieve isotropy by the observations of the velocity redshift relation for extra galactic sources if the value of $\frac{\sigma}{\theta}$ is constant [28,33].

The choice of deceleration parameter is motivated by providing a realistic explanation within modified gravity. The deceleration parameter q measures how the universe's expansion is slowing down because of gravity and other energy components. Many researchers used different forms of deceleration parameter and scale factor for obtaining solution of field equations.

Secondly, for getting the solution of field equations, we have considered different forms of deceleration parameter and mean scale factor such as (i) $q = -1 + \frac{\gamma}{1+a^\gamma}$ (ii) $a(t) = \sinh(\eta t)$ (iii) $a = te^t$

4.1 Model-I

We use a special form of deceleration parameter which is given by Singha and Debnath [37] for FRW model as

$$q = -\frac{a\ddot{a}}{\dot{a}^2} = -1 + \frac{\gamma}{1+a^\gamma} \quad (28)$$

where $\gamma > 0$ is a constant.

After solving Eq. (28), we obtain the Hubble parameter as

$$H = \frac{\dot{a}}{a} = \delta(1 + a^{-\gamma}) \quad (29)$$

where δ is a constant of integration.

On integrating Eq. (29), we obtain mean scale factor as

$$a = (e^{\gamma\delta t} - 1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \quad (30)$$

With the help of Eqs.(20), (27) and (30), the metric potentials A and B are obtained as

$$A = (e^{\gamma\delta t} - 1)^{\frac{3n}{\gamma(n+2)}} \quad (31)$$

$$B = (e^{\gamma\delta t} - 1)^{\frac{3}{\gamma(n+2)}} \quad (32)$$

Using Eqs. (31)-(32) in Eq.(12), we obtain the wet dark fluid Kantowski-Sachs cosmological model in $f(Q, T)$ gravity in the form:

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - (e^{\gamma\delta t} - 1)^{\frac{6n}{\gamma(n+2)}} dr^2 - (e^{\gamma\delta t} - 1)^{\frac{6}{\gamma(n+2)}} [d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2] \quad (33)$$

From Eqs. (21) – (26) with the use of Eqs.(31) – (32), we obtain the physical parameters as follows:

$$V = (e^{\gamma\delta t} - 1)^{\frac{3}{\gamma}} \quad (34)$$

$$H = \delta(1 - e^{-\gamma\delta t})^{-1} \quad (35)$$

$$\theta = 3\delta(1 - e^{-\gamma\delta t})^{-1} \quad (36)$$

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{3\delta^2(n-1)^2}{(n+2)^2} (1 - e^{-\gamma\delta t})^{-2} \quad (37)$$

$$\Delta = \frac{2(n-1)^2}{(n+2)^2}, \quad n \neq -2 \quad (38)$$

$$q = \gamma e^{-\gamma\delta t} - 1 \quad (39)$$

The pressure p_{WDF} is found to be

$$p_{WDF} = \frac{1}{(64\pi^2 + 40\pi\beta + 4\beta^2)} \left\{ \left[k_0 \left(\frac{3}{\gamma(n+2)} - 1 \right) + \frac{9\alpha\delta^2}{(n+2)^2} [8\pi + (1-n)\beta] \right] (1 - e^{-\gamma\delta t})^{-2} + k_0 (1 - e^{-\gamma\delta t})^{-1} \right\} \quad (40)$$

where $k_0 = \frac{6\alpha\gamma\delta^2}{n+2} \left(8\pi + \frac{3\beta}{2} \right)$

For this model, energy density ρ_{WDF} is obtained as

$$\rho_{WDF} = \frac{-9\alpha\delta^2(2n+1)}{(n+2)^2(8\pi + \frac{3\beta}{2})} (1 - e^{-\gamma\delta t})^{-2} + \frac{5\beta/2}{(8\pi + \frac{3\beta}{2})(64\pi^2 + 40\pi\beta + 4\beta^2)} \left\{ \left[k_0 \left(\frac{3}{\gamma(n+2)} - 1 \right) + \frac{9\alpha\delta^2}{(n+2)^2} [8\pi + (1-n)\beta] \right] (1 - e^{-\gamma\delta t})^{-2} + k_0 (1 - e^{-\gamma\delta t})^{-1} \right\} \quad (41)$$

4.2 Model-II

The acceleration phase of the universe is shown by a negative number, while the positive value of the deceleration parameter indicates deceleration phase. Recent cosmological findings suggests that our universe is expanding at an accelerating rate. The deceleration parameter can change smoothly from early deceleration to the present increasing expansion by altering its sign. Consequently, the deceleration parameter has to change with time instead of staying fixed. In order to find a realistic cosmological model of the universe, we use the average scale factor, which yields a time-dependent deceleration parameter. Amirhashchi et al. [38] proposed the average scale factor which is given by,

$$a(t) = \sinh(\eta t) \quad (42)$$

which gives a time-dependent deceleration parameter. Here η is a positive constant. Recently Munde [23] is also used this time dependent scale factor in order to study Kaluza-Klein universe in $f(R, T)$ gravity.

With the help of Eqs.(20), (27) and (42), the metric potentials A and B are obtained as

$$A = [\sinh(\eta t)]^{\frac{3n}{n+2}} \quad (43)$$

$$B = [\sinh(\eta t)]^{\frac{3}{n+2}} \quad (44)$$

Using Eqs. (43) - (44) in Eq.(12), we obtain the wet dark fluid Kantowski-Sachs cosmological model in $f(Q, T)$ gravity in the form:

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - [\sinh(\eta t)]^{\frac{6n}{n+2}} dr^2 - [\sinh(\eta t)]^{\frac{6}{n+2}} [d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2] \quad (45)$$

From Eqs. (21) – (26) with the use of Eqs.(43) – (44), we obtain the physical parameters as follows:

$$V = \sinh^3(\eta t) \quad (46)$$

$$H = \eta \coth(\eta t) \quad (47)$$

$$\theta = 3\eta \coth(\eta t) \quad (48)$$

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{3\eta^2(n-1)^2}{(n+2)^2} \coth^2(\eta t) \quad (49)$$

$$\Delta = \frac{2(n-1)^2}{(n+2)^2}, \quad n \neq -2 \quad (50)$$

$$q = -\tanh^2(\eta t) \quad (51)$$

The pressure p_{WDF} is found to be

$$p_{WDF} = \frac{1}{(64\pi^2 + 40\pi\beta + 4\beta^2)} \left\{ \frac{3\alpha\eta^2}{(n+2)^2} [4\pi(10 - 4n) + 6\beta(1 - n)] \coth^2(\eta t) + \frac{6\alpha\eta^2(8\pi + \frac{3\beta}{2})}{n+2} \right\} \quad (52)$$

For this model, energy density ρ_{WDF} is obtained as

$$\rho_{WDF} = \frac{3\alpha\eta^2}{(n+2)^2(8\pi + \frac{3\beta}{2})} \left\{ \frac{5\beta[4\pi(5-2n) + 3\beta(1-n)]}{(64\pi^2 + 40\pi\beta + 4\beta^2)} - 3(2n + 1) \right\} \coth^2(\eta t) + \frac{15\alpha\beta\eta^2}{(n+2)(64\pi^2 + 40\pi\beta + 4\beta^2)} \quad (53)$$

4.3 Model-III

Following Saha et al. [39] and Pradhan [40], we take average scale factor in the form

$$a(t) = te^t \quad (54)$$

This choice of scale factor gives a time-dependent deceleration parameter. Bhojar et al. [34] used this scale factor for studying Kantowski-Sachs space-time with perfect fluid quadratic equation of state in $f(T)$ gravity. Equation (54) gives physically visible solutions.

With the help of Eqs.(20), (27) and (54), the metric potentials A and B are obtained as

$$A = (te^t)^{\frac{3n}{n+2}} \quad (55)$$

$$B = (te^t)^{\frac{3}{n+2}} \quad (56)$$

Using Eqs. (55) - (56) in equation (12), we obtain the wet dark fluid Kantowski-Sachs cosmological model in $f(Q, T)$ gravity in the form:

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - (te^t)^{\frac{6n}{n+2}} dr^2 - (te^t)^{\frac{6}{n+2}} [d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2] \quad (57)$$

From Eqs. (21) – (26) with the use of Eqs.(55) – (56), we obtain the physical parameters as follows:

$$V = t^3 e^{3t} \quad (58)$$

$$H = 1 + \frac{1}{t} \quad (59)$$

$$\theta = 3 \left(1 + \frac{1}{t} \right) \quad (60)$$

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{3(n-1)^2}{(n+2)^2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{t} \right)^2 \quad (61)$$

$$\Delta = \frac{2(n-1)^2}{(n+2)^2}, \quad n \neq -2 \quad (62)$$

$$q = -1 + \frac{1}{(1+t)^2} \tag{63}$$

The pressure p_{WDF} is found to be

$$p_{WDF} = \frac{1}{(n+2)(64\pi^2+40\pi\beta+4\beta^2)} \left\{ 3\alpha(16\pi+3\beta) \left(1 + \frac{2}{t}\right) + \frac{\alpha[24\pi(5-2n)+18\beta(1-n)]}{n+2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{t}\right)^2 \right\} \tag{64}$$

For this model, energy density ρ_{WDF} is obtained as

$$\rho_{WDF} = \frac{1}{\left(8\pi + \frac{3\beta}{2}\right)} \left\{ \frac{\left(\frac{15\alpha\beta}{2}\right)(16\pi+3\beta)}{(n+2)(64\pi^2+40\pi\beta+4\beta^2)} \left(1 + \frac{2}{t}\right) + \frac{\alpha}{(n+2)^2} \left[\frac{\left(\frac{5\alpha\beta}{2}\right)[24\pi(5-2n)+18\beta(1-n)]}{(64\pi^2+40\pi\beta+4\beta^2)} - 9\alpha(2n+1) \right] \left(1 + \frac{1}{t}\right)^2 \right\} \tag{65}$$

V. DISCUSSION

The mean anisotropy parameter is same for all three models and it is independent of time. The mean anisotropy parameter Δ is useful for deciding whether the model is anisotropic or not. In all the three models, $\Delta = 0$ for $n = 1$ & $\Delta \neq 0$ for $n \neq 1$ i.e. models are anisotropic for $n \neq 1$ and isotropic for $n = 1$. Here all the obtained models are anisotropic throughout.

Fig.1 Plot of Spatial volume vs cosmic time t with $\gamma = 1, \delta = \eta = 2$

Fig.2 Plot of Scale factor vs cosmic time t with $\gamma = 1, \delta = \eta = 2$

Figures 1, 2 demonstrates that special volume and scale factor of the model remain steady initially (time $t = 0$). However, as time advances both start to gradually and consistently increase, ultimately extending toward infinite values over extended period. This significant observation emphasizes that the current models exhibit continuous expansion.

Fig.3 Plot of Hubble parameter vs cosmic time t with $\gamma = 1, \delta = \eta = 2$

Fig.4 Plot of Expansion scalar vs cosmic time t with $\gamma = 1, \delta = \eta = 2$

Fig.5 Plot of Shear scalar vs cosmic time t with $\gamma = 1, n = \delta = \eta = 2$

From Figs. 3, 4 and 5, it is observed that Hubble parameter H , expansion scalar θ and shear scalar σ^2 are infinitely large at time $t = 0$ but with the expansion of the universe, these parameter decreases and halts at a finite value for some finite value of t . The universe grows with time but the speed of expansion reduces to steady value, which shows that the universe starts developing with an infinite rate of expansion. The shear scalar measures the degree of anisotropy in the cosmic growth. A decreasing shear scalar shows that the anisotropy diminishes with time, implying that the universe moves towards a more isotropic state as it develops.

Fig.6 Plot of deceleration parameter vs cosmic time t with $\gamma = 1, \delta = \eta = 2$

Figure 6 shows the evolution trend of deceleration parameter, from which we examine that the evolution of the universe is in accelerating phase at present era. It is observed that q decreases very rapidly and reaches value -1 in all the three models. It is similar to the results of Pradhan [40]. This aligns with latest finding that our universe is in an accelerated expansion.

Fig.7 Plot of Pressure vs cosmic time t with $\alpha = \beta = -1, \gamma = 1, n = \delta = \eta = 2$

Fig.8 Plot of Energy density vs cosmic time t with $\alpha = \beta = -1, \gamma = 1, n = \delta = \eta = 2$

Figure 7 demonstrates the influence of wet dark fluid on the pressure evolution. Pressure p_{WDF} is negative throughout the time of evolution which indicates that the matter behaves like dark energy, gradually increasing from a highly negative value and approaches to a constant value at infinite time. Negative pressure is thought to be necessary for generating an anti-gravity effect that drives the universe's accelerated expansion. Figure 8 depicts the graphical behaviour of energy density. Energy density is positive decreasing function of cosmic time for model-I and II, whereas it is negative increasing function of cosmic time for model-III. For model-I and II, initial density is extremely large and eventually approaches to steady value as $t \rightarrow \infty$. However, energy density

for model-III starts with a negative value, gradually increases over time and approaches to steady negative value in the present. So steady state for pressure and energy density is rapidly achieved in all models.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have studied Kantowski-Sachs cosmological models in the presence of wet dark fluid in $f(Q, T)$ theory of gravity. We have obtained solutions of the field equations in three models by considering special form of deceleration parameter and the average scale factors which gives time dependent deceleration parameter. By inspecting the physical parameters of investigated models, the conclusions are as follows:

- It can be easily seen that in all the three models, the mean anisotropy parameter remains same. The mean anisotropy parameter vanishes at $n = 1$. Thus, our three anisotropic models approach to isotropy at $n = 1$.
- From Figs. 1 and 2, it can be seen that special volume and scale factor of all the models remain steady initially and increases gradually as time increases.
- From Figs. 3, 4 and 5, it is observed that Hubble parameter, expansion scalar and shear scalar of all the models are infinitely large at $t = 0$, but these parameter decreases with the expansion of the universe and halts at a finite value.
- From Fig.7, it is observed that for all models, the pressure is negative throughout the time of evolution gradually increasing from a highly negative value and approaches to a constant value at infinite time which indicates that the matter behaves like dark energy.
- Initial density in model-I and II is extremely large positive and eventually approaches to steady value as $t \rightarrow \infty$. As time progresses, the energy density of model-III increases from a negative value and stabilizes near zero, suggesting that the factors contributing to negative density weaken over time as shown in Fig. 8.
- In all the three models, the graph of deceleration parameter shows that the evolution of the universe is in accelerating phase at present era. It is seen that q decreases very rapidly and reaches value -1 in all the three models. This aligns perfectly with recent observations that our universe is currently undergoing accelerated expansion.

Finally in the obtained models, the study on the Kantowski-Sachs space-time with the form $f(Q, T) = \alpha Q + \beta T$ is carried out. The behavior of various cosmological parameters as discussed above, indicates that the universe is experiencing accelerated expansion. In essence, the current universe is indeed accelerating, which is a significant finding of this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] K.Bamba, S. Capozziello, S.I. Nojiri, S.D.Odintsov, "Dark energy cosmology: the equivalent description via different theoretical models and cosmography tests", *Astrophys. Space Sci.*, Vol. 342, No. 1, pp. 155-228 (2012).
- [2] E.J.Copeland, M. Sami, S.Tsujikawa, "Dynamics of dark energy", *Int. J. Mod. Phys. D*, Vol. 15, No. 11, pp. 1753-1935(2006).
- [3] G.Satyannarayana, T. Vinutha, Y.Sobhanbabu, B.Srinivasu, P.J. Prasuna, M.P.Raju, "Anisotropic Cosmological Model in a Modified Theory of Gravitation", *East Eur. J. Phys.*, Vol. 1, pp. 357-366(2025).
- [4] A.G.Riess et al., "Observational evidence from supernovae for an accelerating universe and a cosmological constant", *Astron. J.*, Vol. 116, No. 3, pp. 1009(1998).
- [5] A.G.Riess et al., "The farthest known supernova: support for an accelerating universe and a glimpse of the epoch of deceleration", *Astrophys. J.*, Vol. 560, No. 1, pp. 49(2001).
- [6] S.Perlmutter et al., "Measurements of Ω and Λ from 42 high-redshift supernovae", *Astrophys. J.*, Vol. 517, No. 2, pp. 565(1999).
- [7] S.I.Nojiri, S.D. Odintsov, P.V.Tretyakov, "Dark energy from modified F (R)-scalar-Gauss-Bonnet gravity", *Phys. Lett. B*, Vol. 651, pp. 224-231(2007).
- [8] H.A.Buchdahl, "Non-linear Lagrangians and cosmological theory", *Mon.Not. R. Astron. Soc.*, Vol. 150, No. 1, pp. 1-8 (1970).
- [9] T.Harko, F.S. Lobo, S.I. Nojiri, S.D. Odintsov, "f (R, T) gravity", *Phys. Rev. D*, Vol. 84, No. 2, pp. 024020 (2011).
- [10] Y.F.Cai, S. Capozziello, M.De Laurentis, E.N.Saridakis, "f (T) teleparallel gravity and cosmology", *Rep. Prog. Phys.*, Vol. 79, No. 10, pp. 106901 (2016).
- [11] J.M.Nester, H.J.Yo, "Symmetric teleparallel general relativity", arXiv preprint gr-qc/9809049 (1998).
- [12] Y.Xu, G. Li, T. Harko, S.D.Liang, "f (Q, T) gravity", *Eur. Phys. J. C*, Vol. 79, No. 8, pp. 708 (2019).
- [13] S.Arora, S.K.J.Pacif, S.Bhattacharjee, P.K.Sahoo, "f (Q, T) gravity models with observational constraints", *Phys. Dark Univ.*, Vol. 30, pp. 100664 (2020).
- [14] S.Arora, A. Parida, P.K. Sahoo, "Constraining effective equation of state in f (Q, T) gravity", *Eur. Phys. J. C*, Vol. 81, No. 6, pp. 555 (2021).
- [15] S.Arora, J.R.L. Santos, P.K.Sahoo, "Constraining f (Q, T) gravity from energy conditions", *Phys. Dark Univ.*, Vol. 31, pp.100790 (2021).

- [16] S.Arora, P.K. Sahoo, "Energy conditions in $f(Q, T)$ gravity", *Phys. Scr.*, Vol. 95, No. 9, pp. 095003(2020).
- [17] A.Nájera, A.Fajardo, J.Cosmol. "Cosmological perturbation theory in $f(Q, T)$ gravity", *Astropart. Phys.*, Vol. 2022, No. 3, pp. 020 (2022).
- [18] G.N.Gadbail, S. Arora, P.K. Sahoo, "Reconstruction of $f(Q, T)$ Lagrangian for various cosmological scenario", *Phys. Lett. B*, Vol. 838, pp. 137710(2023).
- [19] T.H.Loo, R. Solanki, A. De, P.K. Sahoo, "f(Q, T) gravity, its covariant formulation, energy conservation and phase-space analysis", *Eur. Phys. J. C*, Vol. 83, No. 3, pp. 261(2023).
- [20] V.G.Mete, M.T. Sarode, J.S.Wath, "Bianchi Type-V Cosmological Model in $f(Q, T)$ Theory of Gravitation", *Sch J Phys Math Stat*, Vol. 13, No. 1, pp. 49-55(2026).
- [21] P.G.Tait, *The voyage of HMS Challenger (H.M.S.O., London)*, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 1-73(1988).
- [22] A.T.J.Hayward, "Compressibility equations for liquids: a comparative study", *Br. J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol. 18, No. 7, pp.965(1967).
- [23] S.L.Munde, "Kaluza-Klein Universe with Wet Dark Fluid in $f(R, T)$ Theory of Gravity", *Int. J. Sci. & Technol.*, Vol. 12, No. 2, pp.08-15 (2025).
- [24] D.V.Dhote, S.D. Deo, "Plane Symmetric Wet Dark Fluid Model in $f(R)$ Gravitation Theory", *Bulg. J. Phys.*, Vol. 51, pp. 339-351 (2024).
- [25] P.R.Agrawal, A.P. Nile, "Cosmic expansion of Bianchi type-III wet dark fluid model in $f(R)$ theory of gravity", *Int. J. Sci. Res. Arch.*, Vol. 10, No. 2, pp. 350-359(2023).
- [26] S.C.Wankhade, A.S.Nimkar, "Wet Dark Fluid Cosmological Model in Barber Self-Creation Theory of Gravitation", *A.M.Pund, J. Sci. Res.*, Vol. 13, No. 3, pp. 869-878(2021).
- [27] K.M.Singh, S.S. Singh, L. Kumrah, "Evolution of Kaluza-Klein Like Wet Dark Fluid in $f(R, T)$ Theory of Gravitation", arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.03538(2019).
- [28] R.Kantowski, R.K.Sachs, "Some spatially homogeneous anisotropic relativistic cosmological models", *J. Math. Phys.*, Vol. 7, No. 3, pp. 443-446(1966).
- [29] D.Lorenz, "Exact Bianchi-Kantowski-Sachs solutions of Einstein's field equations", *J. Phys. A: Math. Gen.*, Vol. 16, No. 3, pp. 575(1983).
- [30] M.P.Dabrowski, "Note on Kantowski-Sachs universes", *J. Math. Phys.*, Vol. 36, No. 6, p. 2985-2987(1995).
- [31] J.S.Wath, A.S. Nimkar, "Anisotropic dark matter distribution in Saez-Ballester theory of gravitation", *Indian J. Phys.*, Vol. 98, pp. 3011(2024).
- [32] A.Landry, "Kantowski-Sachs spherically symmetric solutions in teleparallel $f(T)$ gravity", *Symmetry*, Vol. 16, No. 8, pp. 953(2024).
- [33] T.Vinutha, K. Niharika, K.S. Kavya, "The study of Kantowski-Sachs perfect fluid cosmological model in modified gravity", *Astrophys.*, Vol. 66, No. 1, pp. 64-83(2023).
- [34] S.R.Bhoyar, V.R.Chirde, S.H. Shekh, "Kantowski-Sachs Cosmological Model with Quadratic Equation of State in $f(T)$ Gravity", *Research & Reviews: Journal of Physics*, Vol. 8, No. 1, pp. 83-91 (2019).
- [35] P.P.Khade, A.P.Wasnik, S.P.Kandalkar, "Kantowski-Sachs Bulk Viscous String Cosmological Model in $f(R, T)$ Gravity with Time Varying Deceleration Parameter", *Global Journal of Science Frontier Research*, Vol. 18, No. 1, pp. 39-46 (2018).
- [36] C.B.Collins, E.N. Glass, D.A.Wilkinson, "Exact spatially homogeneous cosmologies", *Gen.Relativ. Gravit.*, 12, No. 10, pp.805-823(1980).
- [37] A.K.Singha, U. Debnath, "Accelerating universe with a special form of decelerating parameter", *Int. J. Theor. Phys.*, Vol. 48, No. 2, pp. 351-356(2009).
- [38] H.Amirhashchi, A. Pradhan, H. Zainuddin, "An interacting and non-interacting two-fluid dark energy models in FRW universe with time dependent deceleration parameter", *Int. J. Theor. Phys.*, Vol. 50, No. 11, pp. 3529-3543(2011).
- [39] B.Saha, H.Amirhashchi, A.Pradhan, "Two-fluid scenario for dark energy models in an FRW universe-revisited", *Astrophys. Space Sci.*, Vol. 342, No. 1, pp. 257-267(2012).
- [40] A.Pradhan, "Accelerating dark energy models with anisotropic fluid in Bianchi type VI0 space-time", *Res. Astron. Astrophys.*, Vol. 13, No. 2, pp. 139(2013).